

STUDIES IN FRIES MIGRATION. PART IV. THE FRIES MIGRATION OF ACETOXYBENZOIC ACIDS

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The Fries migration of three isomeric acetoxybenzoic acids has been investigated. Aspirin gives 2-hydroxy-5-acetylbenzoic acid, the acetyl group migrating to the *para* position to the hydroxyl group; the *p*-acetoxybenzoic acid on migration gives 3-acetyl-4-hydroxybenzoic acid, the *ortho* migration taking place. Attempts to effect the migration of *m*-acetoxybenzoic acid failed, the *m*-COOH thus hindering the migration. The constitutions of the migration products obtained have been established.

In extension of the work on the Fries migration described in the previous parts of this series (Thakor and Shah, this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 199, 234; Amin and Shah, *ibid.*, 1948, 25, 377) the present investigation was undertaken to study the Fries migration of acetoxy derivatives of the three isomeric hydroxybenzoic acids.

It has been shown earlier that the precise position taken up by the migration group is affected by the nature of the phenol. Rosenmund and Schnurr (*Annalen*, 1928, 460, 56) studied the migration of differently substituted phenolic esters and found that nitro, acetyl and carboxylic groups in the phenol molecule inhibited the reaction. Recently, however, Brown (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 873) has successfully carried out the Fries migration of *o*-nitrophenyl acetate. Cox (*ibid.*, 1930, 52, 352) studied the migration of some esters of methyl salicylate. His results show that the carbomethoxy group in the *ortho* position to the OH group does not hinder the migration. The perusal of literature showed that hardly any work has been done on the application of the Fries migration to the acetoxybenzoic acids. The migration of *o*-acetoxybenzoic acid (aspirin), *m*-, and *p*-acetoxybenzoic acids has been investigated under various conditions and the results are detailed below.

The migration of aspirin gives a product which has been assigned the constitution, 5-acetyl-2-hydroxybenzoic acid (I) on the following grounds: (i) It dissolves in sodium bicarbonate solution with effervescence, and in alkali with yellow colour; (ii) it gives wine-red colour with alcoholic ferric chloride; (iii) it gives an oxime and semicarbazone indicating the presence of ketonic group; (iv) on Clemmensen reduction it gives 5-ethyl-2-hydroxybenzoic acid (II) (Beilstein and Kuhlberg, *J. Russ. phys. chem. Gesell.*, 2, 273; *Annalen*, 1870, 156, 213); (v) it gives a chalkone (III) on condensation with benzaldehyde in presence of alkali, and finally (vi) it is identical with the product obtained by the Friedel-Crafts acetylation of salicylic acid (cf. Krannichfeldt, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 156).

p-Acetoxybenzoic acid was subjected to the Fries migration under different conditions as before. Since the *para* position is occupied, the acetyl group could be expected to go only to the *ortho* position to the hydroxyl group. The migration product has been assigned the constitution 3-acetyl-4-hydroxybenzoic acid (IV) as it dissolves in sodium bicarbonate solution and is

precipitated on acidifying ; it gives red colour with alcoholic ferric chloride indicating the *ortho* position of -OH and -COCH₃ groups ; it gives ester, oxime and semicarbazone confirming the presence of carboxyl and ketonic groups ; it gives a chalkone on condensation with benzaldehyde in presence of alkali.

The Fries migration of 3-acetoxybenzoic acid was tried under various conditions but in all cases the unchanged *m*-hydroxybenzoic acid was recovered ; in no case the migration product could be obtained. Thus, it is evident that the carboxyl group in the *meta* position to hydroxyl group hinders the migration (cf. Mauthner, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1933, ii, 136, 205).

EXPERIMENTAL

For the migration of *o*-acetoxybenzoic acid, the aspirin used in this investigation was of extra pure quality, m.p. 135° and did not give any coloration with ferric chloride.

p-Acetoxybenzoic acid (m.p. 189°) was prepared by acetic anhydride-pyridine method as it was found to give consistently better yield of the pure derivative.

m-Acetoxybenzoic acid (m.p. 129-30°) was prepared by acetic anhydride-concentrated sulphuric acid method.

The migration was carried out (*a*) without a solvent and (*b*) in nitrobenzene as a solvent according to the general method already described in the earlier papers (*loc. cit.*). In each case, several experiments were repeated for the purpose of confirmation. The Fries migration of aspirin in presence of nitrobenzene as a solvent, as well as without it, has been investigated under various conditions of temperature and period of heating. Similarly the migration of *p*-acetoxybenzoic acid was investigated. For sake of uniformity in all experiments 3g. (1 mol.) of the acetoxy-acid was taken and the weights of the products mentioned are of pure products after necessary crystallisation. The migrations were also studied using different proportions of aluminium chloride (1.1, 2.2, 3.3 mols.) and by varying time and temperature of the reaction. To avoid repetition, these experiments have been omitted from the experimental ; only the experiments under the optimum condition are described.

Fries Migration of Aspirin : Formation of 5-Acetyl-2-hydroxybenzoic Acid

(*a*) *In presence of a Solvent.*—To a solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (7g., 3.3 mols.) in dry nitrobenzene (35 c.c.) powdered aspirin (3g., 1 mol.) was added at once. A vigorous reaction set in and HCl fumes were copiously evolved. The reaction mixture was left for one hour at room temperature, protected by a CaCl₂ guard tube to prevent access of moisture, with occasional shaking. Ice and HCl (conc., 5 c.c.) were then added and the mixture was steam-distilled to remove nitrobenzene. The hot residual liquid was filtered through a hot water funnel. The filtrate on cooling deposited white needles, yield 2.5 g. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 216°-17° (mixed m.p. with the product obtained by Friedel-Crafts acetylation of salicylic acid). (Found : C, 59.7 ; H, 4.2 ; equiv., 178.6. C₉H₈O₄ requires C, 60.0 ; H, 4.44 per cent,

Equiv., 180). The acid gives wine-red colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. It is soluble in hot water, alcohol; insoluble in chloroform and benzene.

(b) *Without a Solvent*.—The reactants in the same proportions as above were intimately mixed and heated for one hour on an oil-bath at 120°-125° with calcium chloride guard tube. It was then cooled; ice and concentrated HCl added and the solid separating was collected and crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 216°-17°, yield 1.3g. (the mixed melting point with the above product was unchanged).

The *oxime*, prepared as usual, melted at 180-81° (decomp.). The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 283-84° (decomp.).

2-Hydroxy-5-ethylbenzoic Acid.—The keto-acid (2g.) was reduced according to Clemmensen by using zinc amalgam (10 g.) and hydrochloric acid (1 : 1, 25 c.c.). The hot reaction mixture was filtered; on cooling the filtrate, the reduction product came down; it was crystallised from alcohol in small needles, m.p. 122-23°. It gives blue colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 64.9; H, 5.8; equiv., 165.9. Calc. for $C_9H_{10}O_3$: C, 65.0; H, 6.0 per cent. Equiv., 166).

3-Carboxy-4-hydroxychalkone.—To the mixture of the keto-acid (1g.) dissolved in alcohol (10 c.c.) and benzaldehyde (2c.c.) potassium hydroxide (40%, 10 c.c.) was added slowly and the mixture left overnight. It was then diluted with cold water and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The solid was collected and crystallised from alcohol as yellow needles, m.p. 238° (decomp.). It gives red colour with conc. H_2SO_4 and dissolves in sodium bicarbonate solution with effervescence. (Found : C, 71.2; H, 4.2. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 71.65; H, 4.48 per cent).

Fries Migration of 4-Acetoxybenzoic Acid : Formation of 3-Acetyl-4-hydroxybenzoic Acid

An intimate mixture of aluminium chloride (7g., 3.3 mols.) and 4-acetoxybenzoic acid (3g., 1 mol.) was heated on an oil-bath at 150°-155° for one hour in a flask protected from moisture by a $CaCl_2$ guard tube during heating. HCl fumes were evolved. It was then cooled, treated with ice and HCl; the solid separating was collected and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 240-41°, yield 1.7g. It gives red colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : Equiv, 178.8. $C_9H_8O_4$ requires equiv., 180).

The migration was carried out at 180°-185° without any difference in the amount of the migration product obtained. If, however, nitrobenzene was used as a solvent, no migration product could be obtained.

The *oxime* crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 259-60° (decomp.). The *semicarbazone*, sparingly soluble in most of the common organic solvents, did not melt up to 280°.

The *ethyl ester*, prepared by refluxing the acid and ethyl alcohol in presence of a few drops conc. sulphuric acid on a water-bath for nearly 24 hours, crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 71°. (Found : C, 63.55; H, 5.1. $C_{11}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 63.8; H, 5.2 per cent).

2-Hydroxy-5-carboxychalkone was prepared as before. It crystallised from acetic acid as bright yellow needles, m.p. 222° (decomp.). (Found : C, 71.5; H, 4.4. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 71.65; H, 4.5 per cent).

It gives red colour with conc. sulphuric acid and reddish brown colour with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The results show that three molecules of aluminium chloride are required for the acetyl group to migrate, while with lesser amounts of the same, the cleavage products are formed. The

amount of the deacetylated product increases as the amount of aluminium chloride is decreased. In case of *m*-hydroxybenzoic acid, even with the above proportions or more of the aluminium chloride, no migration could be effected.

In the migration of aspirin in the presence of a solvent, the room temperature is favourable to the migration as the yield of the migration product is good and the reaction is smooth. At higher temperatures, more of the deacetylated product was formed than the product by migration. If the reaction was carried out without a solvent, the same product was obtained in lesser yields; there is no appreciable effect of temperature on the course of the reaction.

In the case of *p*-acetoxybenzoic acid, no migration product is obtained in presence of nitrobenzene as a solvent even though different temperatures are used. But only a white light product of high melting point is obtained. When no solvent is used and the temperature is varied, the migration product is obtained within a range of 150°-180°. It is noteworthy that below 120° no migration takes place; whereas, in case of aspirin, it is best effected at ordinary temperature in presence of a solvent.

The large-scale experiments under the best conditions mentioned above have been tried and good yields of the ketonic acids have been obtained. The results clearly show that the carboxyl group in the *ortho* or *para* position to the hydroxyl group does not retard or inhibit the migration; whereas, it in the *meta* position inhibits it.

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